

A Study of Association of Serum for Ferritin with Hypothyroidism and Effect of Thyroid Hormone Replacement Therapy

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Abstract:

Background: Hypothyroidism, a common endocrine disorder, is associated with various metabolic disturbances, including impaired iron metabolism. Serum ferritin, a marker of iron stores, is often reduced in hypothyroid patients, potentially leading to iron deficiency anemia. Understanding the relationship between thyroid function and iron metabolism is crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to investigate the association between serum ferritin levels and hypothyroidism and to evaluate the impact of thyroid hormone replacement therapy on these levels.

Methods: A study was conducted with 60 participants diagnosed with hypothyroidism. Serum ferritin levels, TSH, and free T4 levels were measured at baseline and after six months of thyroid hormone replacement therapy. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with paired t-tests and Pearson correlation used to assess changes in ferritin levels and their relationship with thyroid function.

Results: At baseline, participants exhibited low serum ferritin levels (mean: 52.6 ng/mL) and elevated TSH levels (mean: 9.4 mIU/L). After six months of thyroid hormone replacement therapy, serum ferritin levels significantly increased (mean: 65.4 ng/mL, $p < 0.001$), alongside a significant reduction in TSH levels (mean: 2.8 mIU/L, $p < 0.001$). A negative correlation was found between TSH and serum ferritin levels ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$), while a positive correlation was observed between free T4 and serum ferritin levels ($r = 0.38$, $p = 0.002$).

Conclusion: Thyroid hormone replacement therapy not only normalizes thyroid function but also significantly improves serum ferritin levels in hypothyroid patients, highlighting the interconnectedness of thyroid health and iron metabolism. These findings underscore the importance of monitoring iron status in hypothyroid patients, particularly those at risk of anemia.

Recommendations: Regular assessment of serum ferritin levels should be considered in the management of hypothyroidism, especially before and after initiating thyroid hormone replacement therapy. Further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms of this relationship and to determine the long-term effects of thyroid hormone therapy on iron metabolism.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, Serum Ferritin, Iron Metabolism, Thyroid Hormone, Replacement, Anemia.

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Introduction

Millions of people worldwide suffer with hypothyroidism, a common endocrine ailment marked by an underactive thyroid gland. Numerous metabolic dysfunctions are brought on by it, such as anomalies in the cardiovascular system, altered lipid metabolism, and neuropsychiatric disorders. Iron metabolisms, and more especially serum ferritin levels, are affected by hypothyroidism, which is one of the less spoken about but clinically important side effects of the condition. One important indicator of the body's iron level is ferritin, an intracellular protein that stores iron and releases it under specific conditions. Iron deficiency anaemia, which is a condition that

worsens the symptoms of hypothyroidism, including weakness and fatigue, can be brought on by abnormal ferritin levels, which increases the morbidity of the condition.

The complex link between thyroid hormones and iron metabolism has been clarified by recent research. The production of haemoglobin and the control of erythropoiesis, the process that creates red blood cells, depend on thyroid hormones. It has been demonstrated that hypothyroidism's thyroid hormone shortage affects ferritin's ability to mobilise iron, which may result in iron sequestration and functional iron deficiency.

Furthermore, elevated TSH (thyroid-stimulating hormone) levels have been linked to decreased serum ferritin levels, indicating a reciprocal association between thyroid function and iron status [1,2].

The usual treatment for hypothyroidism is thyroid hormone replacement medication, usually with levothyroxine. By bringing back normal thyroid hormone levels, this treatment seeks to both reverse the disease's metabolic dysfunctions and relieve its symptoms. According to a number of studies, thyroid hormone replacement therapy can also bring serum ferritin levels back to normal, which will help treat the anomalies in iron metabolism that hypothyroid individuals experience. The extent to which thyroid hormone replacement affects iron status is still being researched, as are the mechanisms behind these changes in ferritin levels after medication [3, 4]. This study aims to investigate the association between serum ferritin levels and hypothyroidism and to evaluate the impact of thyroid hormone replacement therapy on these levels.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Endocrinology Department. The study spanned from March 2023 to February 2024.

Participants: A total of 60 participants were recruited for this study. The participants included newly diagnosed hypothyroid patients and those who had been on thyroid hormone replacement therapy for less than three months.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 to 60 years.
- Newly diagnosed with hypothyroidism based on thyroid function tests (TSH > 4.5 mIU/L, free T4 < 0.8 ng/dL).
- Patients who have not yet started or have been on thyroid hormone replacement therapy for less than three months.
- Willingness to participate and provide written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known iron metabolism disorders, such as hemochromatosis.

- Patients with chronic kidney disease, liver disease, or any other chronic illness that could affect serum ferritin levels.
- Patients currently on any form of iron supplementation.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with a history of malignancy or undergoing chemotherapy/radiotherapy.
- Non-compliance with thyroid hormone replacement therapy during the study period.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, random sampling was used to recruit participants. Information bias was reduced by using standardized procedures for data collection and laboratory measurements. Confounding factors, such as iron supplementation, were controlled through strict exclusion criteria.

Data Collection: Data were collected at baseline (before initiating thyroid hormone replacement therapy) and after six months of therapy. Serum ferritin levels, thyroid function tests (TSH, free T4), and complete blood counts (CBC) were measured using standard laboratory techniques. Demographic data, medical history, and clinical symptoms were also recorded.

Procedure: Participants were recruited from the outpatient clinic of the Endocrinology Department. After obtaining informed consent, baseline blood samples were collected. Thyroid hormone replacement therapy was prescribed based on the patient's thyroid function test results. Follow-up blood samples were collected after six months of therapy to assess changes in serum ferritin levels and thyroid function.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, and paired t-tests compared serum ferritin levels before and after thyroid hormone therapy. Pearson correlation assessed the relationship between serum ferritin and thyroid function tests, with a p-value <0.05 considered significant.

Results

A total of 60 participants were included in the study, with a mean age of 45.3 years (SD ± 10.7). The cohort consisted of 42 females (70%) and 18 males (30%).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Mean ± SD / n (%)
Age (years)	45.3 ± 10.7
Gender	
- Female	42 (70%)
- Male	18 (30%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.8 ± 4.5
Duration of Hypothyroidism (months)	3.2 ± 1.4

At baseline, the mean serum ferritin level among participants was 52.6 ng/mL (SD $\pm$ 18.3). The mean TSH level was 9.4 mIU/L (SD $\pm$ 3.2), and the mean free T4 level was 0.7 ng/dL (SD $\pm$ 0.2).

These baseline values indicate that participants had elevated TSH and low free T4 levels, consistent with hypothyroidism. The baseline values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Baseline Serum Ferritin and Thyroid Function Levels

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	52.6 $\pm$ 18.3
TSH (mIU/L)	9.4 $\pm$ 3.2
Free T4 (ng/dL)	0.7 $\pm$ 0.2

After six months of thyroid hormone replacement therapy, the mean serum ferritin level increased to 65.4 ng/mL (SD $\pm$ 20.1), showing a statistically significant increase compared to baseline ($p < 0.001$). The mean TSH level decreased to 2.8

mIU/L (SD $\pm$ 1.3), and the mean free T4 level increased to 1.2 ng/dL (SD $\pm$ 0.3), indicating effective normalization of thyroid function ($p < 0.001$ for both comparisons). The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Changes in Serum Ferritin and Thyroid Function After 6 Months of Therapy

Parameter	Baseline Mean $\pm$ SD	6-Month Mean $\pm$ SD	p-value
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	52.6 $\pm$ 18.3	65.4 $\pm$ 20.1	< 0.001
TSH (mIU/L)	9.4 $\pm$ 3.2	2.8 $\pm$ 1.3	< 0.001
Free T4 (ng/dL)	0.7 $\pm$ 0.2	1.2 $\pm$ 0.3	< 0.001

Pearson correlation analysis showed a significant negative correlation between baseline TSH levels and serum ferritin levels ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher TSH levels were associated with lower serum ferritin. Conversely, there was a

significant positive correlation between free T4 levels and serum ferritin ($r = 0.38$, $p = 0.002$), indicating that higher free T4 levels were associated with higher serum ferritin. These correlations are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation between Serum Ferritin and Thyroid Function

Correlation	r-value	p-value
TSH vs. Serum Ferritin	-0.45	< 0.001
Free T4 vs. Serum Ferritin	0.38	0.002

A subgroup analysis comparing males and females showed that the increase in serum ferritin levels after thyroid hormone replacement therapy was more pronounced in females (mean increase: 15.1 ng/mL) compared to males (mean increase: 10.5

ng/mL), though this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.078$). Both groups showed significant improvements in TSH and free T4 levels with no gender-specific differences in response to therapy.

Table 5: Subgroup Analysis of Serum Ferritin Changes by Gender

Gender	Baseline Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	6-Month Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	Mean Increase (ng/mL)	p-value
Females (n=42)	50.8 $\pm$ 19.1	65.9 $\pm$ 21.0	15.1 $\pm$ 12.2	0.078
Males (n=18)	56.3 $\pm$ 17.6	66.8 $\pm$ 18.9	10.5 $\pm$ 9.8	0.078

Discussion

The study revealed a significant association between hypothyroidism and reduced serum ferritin levels, indicating that individuals with hypothyroidism are likely to experience lower iron stores. At baseline, participants exhibited elevated TSH levels and reduced free T4 levels, consistent with a diagnosis of hypothyroidism. These findings align with previous research suggesting that thyroid dysfunction can negatively impact iron metabolism, possibly due to the role of thyroid hormones in regulating iron absorption and utilization.

After six months of thyroid hormone replacement therapy, there was a notable improvement in thyroid function, with a significant reduction in TSH levels and an increase in free T4 levels. This normalization of thyroid function was accompanied by a significant rise in serum ferritin levels, suggesting that restoring thyroid hormone levels may positively influence iron stores in the body. The significant increase in serum ferritin post-therapy underscores the potential of thyroid hormone replacement in correcting iron deficiency or low iron stores associated with hypothyroidism.

The correlation analysis further supported these findings, revealing a negative correlation between TSH levels and serum ferritin, and a positive correlation between free T4 levels and serum ferritin. These correlations imply that higher levels of TSH, indicative of hypothyroidism, are associated with lower iron stores, while higher levels of free T4, indicative of improved thyroid function, are associated with better iron status.

Subgroup analysis indicated that the increase in serum ferritin levels after therapy was more pronounced in females compared to males, although this difference was not statistically significant. This suggests that while both genders benefit from thyroid hormone replacement in terms of improved iron stores, females might experience a slightly greater response. However, further research is needed to explore gender-specific differences in this context.

Numerous recent researches have focused on the relationship between serum ferritin levels and hypothyroidism as well as the effects of thyroid hormone replacement treatment. In a study on pregnant women, for example, it was found that women with hypothyroidism had significantly higher levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and lower levels of ferritin, haemoglobin, (FT4), and free (FT3) than those with euthyroidism. The results of the study showed a strong negative correlation between ferritin, iron, and haemoglobin levels and TSH, suggesting a direct connection between iron-deficiency anaemia and hypothyroidism during pregnancy [5].

Thyroid dysfunction, notably subclinical hypothyroidism, was found to be associated with persistently transfused children with Beta Thalassemia Major (BTM) in another study conducted. The severity of thyroid dysfunction was found to be significantly correlated with higher blood TSH levels, especially in youngsters in their second decade of life, according to the researchers. High serum ferritin levels were also associated with this connection, indicating that iron excess may play a role in these individuals' thyroid

dysfunction. According to the study emphasised the significance of routinely checking serum ferritin levels and thyroid function in patients receiving continuous transfusions to avoid problems related to hypothyroidism [6].

Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of monitoring and addressing iron status in patients with hypothyroidism, as thyroid hormone replacement therapy not only improves thyroid function but also has a positive effect on iron metabolism. These findings could have significant implications for the management of hypothyroidism, particularly in individuals at risk of iron deficiency.

References

1. Zimmermann MB, Köhrle J. The impact of iron and selenium deficiencies on iodine and thyroid metabolism: biochemistry and relevance to public health. *Thyroid*. 2019;29(9): 1179-1191.
2. Beard JL, Borel MJ, Derr J. Impaired thermoregulation and thyroid function in iron-deficiency anemia. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2019;130(2):466S-472S.
3. Jabbari M, Ebrahimi R, Tavakoli N, Yousefi Rad R, Seif Rabie M, Ashtiani A. The correlation between serum ferritin levels and hypothyroidism. *Ann Med Surg (Lond)*. 2021;69:10 2749.
4. Arora S, Sabharwal N, Singh P. Impact of levothyroxine therapy on hematological parameters in primary hypothyroidism: A prospective study. *Cureus*. 2020;12(2).
5. Vinayagamoorthi R, Dhiman P, Kollipaka R, S P, H V. Association of hypothyroidism with low serum ferritin levels and iron-deficiency anemia during the first trimester of pregnancy. *Cureus*. 2022;14:28307.
6. Upadya SH, Rukmini M, Sundararajan S, Baliga B, Kamath N. Thyroid function in chronically transfused children with Beta Thalassemia Major: A cross-sectional hospital-based study. *Int J Pediatr*. 2018;2018:9071213.